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Biometric Analysis of Research Articles On Job Crafting Published In National Refereed Journals Indexed By ULAKBIM

Doç. Dr. Esra AYDIN GÖKTEPE¹, Dr. Öğr.Gör. Gülşah ERDEM^{2}*

¹ İşletme, İktisadi İdari Bilimler Fakültesi, İstanbul Arel Üniversitesi, İstanbul, Türkiye.

esraaydingoktepe@arel.edu.tr

² Yabancı Diller, Yabancı Diller Yüksekokulu, Ankara Sosyal Bilimler Üniversitesi, Ankara, Türkiye

gulsah.erdem@asbu.edu.tr

Abstract

The concept of job crafting is a new approach in the process of job design. This approach is in line with the changes we face in all areas of life since employees become active agents in their work life. Thus, they design their jobs proactively rather than the manager's initiative. The aim of this study is to conduct a bibliometric analysis in the context of job crafting and to determine the trends of publications on this subject and to identify new research areas. In order to achieve this goal, a bibliometric analysis of the publications on "job crafting" published in the ULAKBIM database between 2017 and 2023 was aimed. According to the ULAKBIM database, there are a total of 50 publications dealing with job crafting. These publications were analyzed in terms of type of publication, year of publication, sector in which the research was conducted, research method and other concepts that are related to the variables subject to the research. As a result of the search in the ULAKBIM database, it was determined that the relationship between job crafting and leadership, organizational culture, job satisfaction, work-life conflict, perceived organizational support, five factor personality traits, organizational commitment was discussed in a limited number of publications.

Keywords: Job crafting, biometric analysis

1. Introduction

In today's dynamic work environment, the main goal of organizations is to boost the performances of employees and the utility of organizations. One way of achieving this goal is designing jobs so that workers can perform fully and maximize their performances and that of organizations. The concept of job designing functions as a top-down process. Because of that reason, it has some drawbacks such as not including all employees since it cannot address the needs or

* Yazışılan yazar/Corresponding author: *Gülşah ERDEM*

¹ <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7833-448X> , ² <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9598-3756>

the interests of them. In addition, this process may not help workers internalize it deeply. Nowadays the role of an individual in an organization increases. That is why this situation leads to a born of new concept called job crafting. The main difference of this concept is that it is based on a bottom-up process. In other words, a worker can craft the job on his or her interest without taking into consideration of the benefit of the organization. The important point is it is not done intentionally, rather the focus stands on the advantage of the worker not that of the organization. As it is a neutral process, an organization may benefit or harm from it. On the other hand, it is essential to mention that it increases individual performance, so this generally becomes advantageous on behalf of the organization as well. Another point is it is not preferred by all employees since it flows naturally especially for the ones with a proactive personality. The motives behind that action stem from psychological, physiological, and social needs. While crafting a job, a worker may alter the task, the meaning or the relations related to the job. As mentioned before, it is highly crucial for organizations to pay their attention on the workers. Since job crafting is mainly an individual-based (worker-based) process, the number of studies is also increasing in parallel with its importance. Thus, in this research the concept of job crafting is handled with other variables and analysed in related contexts. The conceptual framework is built with this purpose and by conducting a bibliometric analysis of publications in ULAKBİM database between 2017-2023 on the subject job crafting, deficiencies in conceptual analysis and field research were identified and new areas of study were identified.

2. Conceptual Framework

Under this title the concept of ‘job crafting’ is analyzed and its relations with other variables are also discussed and explained. The datasets used and/or analyzed during the current study are available.

2.1. The concept of job crafting

Unlike the previous understanding that defined job designing as a top-down top and “one-size-fits-all” perspectives initiated by the organization [1] a bottom-up, individualized, participative process where employees take active roles was first mentioned by Kulik et. al. [2].

The concept of "job crafting" was introduced in business literature by Wrzesniewski and Dutton (2001) They defined it as “the physical and cognitive changes individuals make in the task or relational boundaries of their work”. The background of this concept is derived from the ideas of “role innovation” by Katz and Khan (1966). The concept is used to describe the activities employees undertake to reformulate, change and reshape their jobs. Wrzesniewski and Dutton (2001) defined three fundamental and universal motivations driving job crafting-(basic human needs) need for control over job and work meaning; need for human connection and need for positive self-image [3].

Tims and Bakker defined job crafting as “For the purpose of balancing job requirement and resources, employees makes change in their behavior according to their ability and needs.” This definition’s perspective is based on a Job-Demands and Resource (JD-R) model. This model separates working conditions into two as “job demands” and “job resources,” and clarifies their impact on performances by shaping employee well-being (burnout and work engagement). In the same way, it demonstrates how proactive and reactive behaviours of employees affect job demands and resources [4].

As it is seen from these definitions, the main streams of job crafting are categorized into two concepts; one is role-based, the other is resource-based [5]. Depending on these two distinctive approaches; current definitions integrating these elements of job crafting seem to be dominant. It appears that these two approaches are integrated in current/ recent definitions.

According to Demetroui ‘Job crafting is the process by which workers modify the resources and demands of their jobs to make their own work more meaningful, engaging, and satisfying.’ Job crafting as adjustments and self-initiated changes employees make and strategies they use to optimize their jobs in terms of different boundaries, needs and demands [6]. Job crafting (JC) refers to self-initiated changes that employees introduce to their jobs to optimize their job design and increase the fit between the job and their needs and preferences” [7].

What the common point of various definitions lies in the changes job holders make in order to improve their work in a meaningful way [8]. What we understand from these definitions is employees alter their work-related roles in a new way creatively.

2.2. Different perspectives of job crafting

Job crafting has three dimensions; task, relational, and cognitive. When employees craft their jobs in terms of task, they are able to change the nature or characteristics of the job given by formal job descriptions by modifying the amount and the content of the job. In relational terms, employees change the way they interact by determining the degree of depth and scope. In cognitive terms, employees alter their perceptions of their work to find their jobs more meaningful [3], [9].

From Tims perspective, job crafting has four dimensions; increasing social job resources (e.g., attempting to enhance competence), increasing structural job resources (i.e. getting support from colleagues), increasing challenging job demands (i.e. undertaking new tasks voluntarily), and decreasing hindering job demands (lessening the burden of job

demands). The first three job crafting dimensions are associated with positive outcomes while the last one indicates a different result [10], [11].

Through lenses of Leena, Appelbaum and Shevchuk (2009), job crafting assumes a collaborative role as well as individual characteristics. Unlike individual initiated processes, changes (psychological, physiological, and social) take place at group level. Work environment and the characteristics of the job itself become essential indicators in this context. [12].

In recent studies, job crafting moves beyond these two main conceptualisation (role-resource based) and gains a new perspective; “approach job crafting” and “avoidance job crafting”. The former aims to increase positive outcomes of work; the latter aims to prevent negative outcomes of work [13]. They are conceptualized in different terms as “promotion-focused job crafting” and “prevention focused job crafting” in a study conducted by a lots of researchers [14], [15], [16], [5]. Paralel to these perspectives, two key factors have been put forward in this literature; proactive and reactive motives. While proactive motives are based on achieving goals; reactive motives are based on refraining from uneasiness [17].

As people have a life out of work, they also have a tendency to craft in the other domain as well. The concept of crafting on the other domain was first introduced as “leisure crafting” by Berg, Grant and Johnson (2010). Leisure crafting is performed by leisure crafters who reengineer their task and relational boundaries of their time out of work [18]. The problem with this term is that it is handled as a very broad concept, even though it represents only a part of the non-work domain and does not cover the home activities (Petrou and Bakker, 2016). . Emphasizing that point, home crafting has been conceptualized by Demerouti et al. (2019). It was categorized into three types; seeking resources, seeking challenges and reducing demands. [19],[20].

Alongside domain-based perspectives (e.g. job-crafting, leisure crafting, home crafting, work-life balance crafting) holistic life-crafting model encloses multiple dimensions of an individual’s life with the aim of achieving purpose, meaning, and wellbeing. This model differs from other perspectives in employing crafting strategies with meaningful goals in all other parts of lives [21].

Job crafting has been analyzed from “agent – recipient” perspective in a social context from Roczniewska and Marszałek [22]. In this study agents have active roles whereas recipients have passive roles in modifying their work. Empowering “agency” becomes a highly crucial strategy in achieving job crafting goals. All these approaches convey multiple insights of the concept of job crafting under the main context of crafting.

2.3. Job crafting from organizational perspective

It is clearly seen that job crafting is based on an individual effort- employee-centered process. As innovative, creative and proactive employees, job crafters tend to take action to redesign their businesses. While job crafting is primarily beneficial for employees, it also has implications for organizations as organizational interventions have the capacity to facilitate or encourage it [23]. The outcomes of the performance of job crafters are in line with the performance of organizations. It becomes a two-ended process in terms of performance, contributing to the health of employees and the effectiveness of organizations. Since organizations can also take advantage of the positive nature and experiences of employees, they can transform these changes to the benefit of organizational goals. Thus, when organizations take an active role by increasing awareness of this process, the possible impacts that may disturb organizations will be prevented [17], [24]. [25] [26]. As the importance of perceived organizational support and employees' sense of power has impacts on job crafting and its outcomes, it is crucial that managers enable a context in which employees perform job crafting that is aligned with organizational objectives. The impact of managers and organizations on employee well-being is also delineated in Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) model [27], [28], [29],[30].

On the contrary, the process of job crafting does not always guarantee a positive result. In some cases, it may leave undesired effects on employees performance and organizational goals due to some unpleasant situations (frustration, stress, failure, workload, pressure, work-family conflict). It may even weaken well-being [19], [8], [31],[32].

These studies reveal that organizations have important roles in turning the crafting process into an advantage and preventing it from becoming a disadvantage. It is clear that organizations can mainly benefit from job crafting of employees by encouraging them to pursue crafting initiatives. Additionally, organizational support facilitates that process.

2.4. Antecedents of job crafting

Researches conducted by various scholars in the literature demonstrate that this concept is influenced by several influential factors.

According to Peng (2018) the antecedents of job crafting is divided into two categories: Individual and environmental factors; individual factors encompass proactive personality, personal motivational orientation, regulatory focus. Meanwhile, environmental factors include discretion, decision latitude and job autonomy, supportive organizational climate, more autonomy in their work [33].

Kim, Im, and Qu (2018), classified antecedent factors into three categories: perceived organizational support as organizational-related, autonomy as task-related, and creative self-efficacy as individual-related [34]. In line with this, Zang and Parker (2019), expanded the scope, identifying job characteristics, individual differences, motivational characteristics, and social context as four critical antecedents of job crafting [35]. Moreover, Park and Park (2023), extended this understanding by grouping contextual antecedents into four distinct categories: job, group, leadership, and organizational characteristics [36].

A research emphasizes the intrinsic and extrinsic motivators of job crafting. The intrinsic factors are job autonomy, self-efficacy and proactivity; the extrinsic factors are career expectations and the intent to stay or quit the organization; the role of external regulation (e.g. expectations of social and material rewards or fear of punishment) [37]. Another study also reveals the motivators of job crafting as the need for positive self-image, work experience, self-efficacy [38].

Van Belle et al. (2019) asserted that high levels of autonomy and high workload are vital contributors of job crafting [39]. Additionally, Lazazzara, Tims, and Gennaro (2019) highlighted the significance of social support and a strong organizational culture in shaping job crafting behaviors [40]. Philip (2021) emphasized how proactive traits and political skills facilitate overall job crafting efforts [41]. Furthermore, Wang, Li, and Chen (2020) pointed out the pivotal role of the social context of work, particularly involving organizational insiders, in shaping employees' job crafting behavior [42].

Furthermore, Irfan et al. (2023) noted that relational job resources (co-worker relationship quality) stimulate job crafting and sustainable employability [43]. Moreover, Niessen, Weseler, and Kostova emphasize the significance of the need for a positive self-image, work experience, and self-efficacy as motivators for job crafting [44].

Leadership is another factor influencing job crafting. Transformational leadership and empowering leadership foster job crafting positively [45], [46]. Humble leadership is characterized as bottom-up leadership, thus it has positive relations with job crafting [47].

Job crafting is linked to individual differences (e.g., demographics, personality) and job characteristics. In terms of gender, women have a higher capacity for job crafting compared to men [1].

These findings collectively underscore the multifaceted nature of job crafting and the diverse influences that contribute to its dynamics in the workplace.

2.5. Outcomes of job crafting

In the literature, job crafting can lead to a variety of outcomes. Most of the research on the outcomes of job crafting highlight its positive and significant impacts [48].

The outcomes are based on three factors; meaning of work, work identity and well-being [49]. Literature highlights innovative work behavior; employee well-being [50], [51]. Cheng (2016) emphasizes both individual and collaborative crafting's beneficial effect on employees' satisfaction with their jobs, commitment to the organization, and job performance [52].

Job crafting has demonstrated strong connections with employees' job attitudes, occupational well-being, and various forms of work performance as highlighted in Rudolph's study (2017). [48] The research of Devotto and Wechsler (2019) echoed this, indicating favorable effects of job crafting behaviors on employee well-being and job performance [53]. Additionally, researchers found that higher levels of work engagement were associated with elevated performance levels, emphasizing the importance of job crafting in this process [54]. Studies such as van den Heuvel et al. (2015), have shown that increased self-efficacy due to job crafting can contribute to higher positive affect and reduced negative affect, ultimately enhancing well-being [55]. Mansour and Tremblay (2020) further support this by suggesting that job crafting can lead to employees feeling more energized and experiencing personal growth within their roles [56]. Moreover, Wang, Li, and Chen's research (2020), underscores the crucial role of job crafting in translating social resources into improved work outcomes." [57].

Reframing jobs paves the way for employees to enrich their jobs, expand their job roles and ensure work engagement. They affect each other like dominoes; enriching jobs lead to focusing on the characteristics of the jobs, resulting in work engagement [58].

All these studies reveal that when job crafting is embraced effectively, it can give rise to positive outcomes for both individuals and organizations. Unlike the positive outcomes, hindering the negative ones is also an important strategy on behalf of the organizations.

3. Bibliometric Analysis of ULAKBIM Indexed Articles Containing Job Crafting Concepts Between 2003-2023

3.1. Aim of the research

The aim of the study is to provide a holistic perspective on the studies conducted in the field of "job crafting" and to offer new areas of study to researchers through a bibliometric analysis of the publications on "job crafting" published

between 2003-2023 in the journals included in the National Academic Network and Information Center (ULAKBIM) index in the national literature.

3.2. Originality of the research

This study, which deals with job crafting, provides originality criteria that will contribute to the field due to the limited number of publications dealing with the concept of job crafting in the literature and the lack of bibliometric analysis of ULAKBIM indexed publications on job crafting.

3.3. Research questions

The aim of this research is to examine studies investigating concepts related to job requirements, and answers to the questions listed below have been sought in this study:

- ✓ What are the publication languages of research on job crafting?
- ✓ What are the research methods used in research on job crafting?
- ✓ In which sectors have studies on job crafting been conducted?
- ✓ What is the publication year distribution of research on job crafting?
- ✓ What are the other research variables addressed in research on job crafting?

3.4. Research method

Bibliometric analysis method, one of the quantitative research methods, was used to answer the research questions. It is defined as “bibliometric analysis is a popular and rigorous method for exploring and analyzing large volumes of scientific data.” [59].

3.5. Research findings

Publications on "job crafting" published in Turkish and English between 2003 and 2023, with open access to full texts, were classified in terms of publication language, research method, research sector, other related variables and publication language.

3.5.1. Distribution of ULAKBIM Indexed Articles on Job Crafting by Language of Publication

The distribution of ULAKBIM indexed articles containing the concept of job crafting in terms of language of publication was analyzed and given in Table 1.

Table 1. Distribution of Publication Language of Studies on Job Crafting

As given in Table 1, it was determined that 9 of the 49 articles were prepared in English and 40 in Turkish.

3.5.2. Distribution of ULAKBIM Indexed Articles on Job Crafting by Research Method

ULAKBIM indexed articles on job crafting are analyzed in terms of research method and given in Table 2.

Table 2. Distribution of Studies on Job Crafting in terms of Research Method

As given in Table 2, it was determined that 2 articles addressed the concept of job crafting with conceptual analysis method, 39 with quantitative research methods and 8 with qualitative research methods.

3.5.3. Sectoral Distribution of ULAKBIM Indexed Articles Containing the Concept of Job Crafting

ULAKBIM indexed articles containing job crafting concepts are analyzed in terms of sectoral analysis of research fields and given in Table 3.

Table 3. Distribution of Studies on Job Crafting

As given in Table 3, it was determined that 4 articles dealt with the concept of job crafting in the banking and finance sector, 10 in the education sector, 4 in the aviation sector, 5 in the public sector, 10 in the production sector, 6 in the health sector and 10 in the service sector.

3.5.4. Distribution of ULAKBIM Indexed Articles Containing the Concept of Job Crafting by Year of Publication

The year of publication distribution of ULAKBIM indexed articles containing the concept of job crafting is given in Table 4.

Table 4. Distribution of Studies on Job Crafting According to Years of Publication

As seen in Table 4, the distribution of the number of studies by years does not show a significant acceleration.

3.5.5. Distribution of ULAKBIM Indexed Articles Containing the Concept of Job Crafting in Terms of Other Related Variables

The distribution of ULAKBIM indexed articles containing the concept of job crafting in terms of their relationships with other research variables is given in Table 5.

Table 5. Distribution of the Studies on the Concept of Job Crafting in Terms of Their Relationship with Other Research Variables

As seen in Table 5, job crafting is most frequently associated with negative work attitudes, followed by leadership, personality, job dedication, job satisfaction, organizational culture, work-life balance, and passion for work. The other visual given in Table 5 includes the sum of rarely discussed variables such as alienation from work, meaningfulness of work, locus of control, self-efficacy, boredom at work.

4. Discussion and Conclusions

In today's dynamic work life, the roles of employees are not only designed by managers for the advantages of organizations, but also shaped by the employees' initiative with the aim to fit their needs and indirectly the needs of organizations. This way of design is called job crafting. The concept of job crafting is a way of examining the activities of employees from a new perspective and is an issue that needs to be addressed in terms of its organizational significance.

In this study, in which the bibliometric analysis of the studies on job crafting was conducted, it was determined that Turkish publications on job crafting were more than the publications in English. In light of this result, it is recommended to increase the number of publications in English in order for publications on job crafting to be cited and to be visible in the international literature.

It has been determined that quantitative studies on job crafting are more common than qualitative and conceptual studies. This result can be explained by the fact that there is a "Job Crafting Scale" developed to measure job crafting and a validity and reliability study was conducted. In addition, although job crafting is a new research variable in the national literature, it was determined that there is a limited number of conceptual analysis studies in the bibliographic analysis. This result suggests that in order to fill the gap in the literature, researchers are recommended to conduct conceptual research in the field of job crafting and identify the theories on which the concept of job crafting is based.

It has been determined that studies on job crafting are mostly examined in the education and service sectors, while there is a limited number of studies in the aviation, banking and finance sectors. However, it has been determined that there are not enough studies for education and service sectors to make sectoral comments. There is a need to increase the number of studies on job crafting in education and service sectors, primarily in aviation, banking and finance sectors.

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